

THE MICRO-MECHANICS OF CRACK GROWTH IN FIBRE COMPOSITES: OBSERVING AND MODELLING THE FAILURE PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT

Successful modelling of physical processes in materials can be achieved by following a set of steps: identify the physical mechanisms (preferably by direct observation); construct the model (using previously modelled problems or applying existing modelling tools); test the model (by comparing with data) and tune the model (lumping together empirical parameters). In other words, determine the dominant mechanism(s); simplify it (them); and exploit the modelling successes of others in materials science and engineering.

This paper presents a modelling strategy for analyzing the tensile failure of notched carbon fibre laminates over a range of elevated temperature.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade we have developed a successful modelling strategy for analyzing the failure of a variety of fibre reinforced polymer matrix composite laminates under tensile loading[1-15]. The conditions investigated have included, monotonic quasi-static, cyclic fatigue and static fatigue for a range of environmental conditions. In the case of carbon fibre laminates, the key observation that made possible the development of a relatively simple model is that the sub-critical damage, consisting of matrix cracks (splits in 0° plies, transverse ply cracks and delaminations between plies), grows in a more or less self-similar manner. This observation enables the prediction of damage orientation with applied load to be considerably simplified.

DAMAGE OBSERVED AROUND NOTCHES

An X-ray image of a typical (90/0)_s notched tensile specimen of carbon fibre in epoxy loaded in tension is shown in Fig. 1. The dark images of the photograph indicate three forms of matrix crack emanating from within the notch tip damage zone:

- (1) *splitting* in the 0° plies;
- (2) *delamination* zones at 90/0 interfaces whose size is related to split length; and
- (3) *transverse ply cracking* in the 90° plies.

A concentration of fibre breaks in the 0° plies occurs at the intersection of a split and a transverse ply crack.

In a monotonic tensile test or in a cyclic loading experiment, the shape of the damage zone remains unaffected; it simply grows in size. The rate of damage growth is greater for laminates having thicker plies.

In the example above, notch tip damage grows in a self-similar manner, with the characteristic triangular-shaped delamination zone at the (90/0) interfaces. At the tip of the split, the delamination angle, (between about 1° and 7°) depends, for example, on ply thickness, matrix toughness, temperature, moisture content, and so forth. Essentially, the damage pattern at the notch tip can be characterised by the delamination angle and split length. This ignores the transverse ply cracks in the matrix which are important but they can play a secondary role.

Figures 1 and 2 *Geometry of a Split and Delamination in 1/8th of a [90/0]_s Specimen*

MODELLING DAMAGE IN MONOTONIC LOADING

The change in potential energy of a system as a crack grows is given by the change in strain energy less the work done by the applied loads. For an infinitesimal amount of crack growth, the energy released under fixed load or fixed displacement conditions is equal to:

$$\delta E_r = \frac{1}{2} P \delta u \quad (1)$$

where P is the remote load, u is the imposed remote displacement.

As we have shown, the growth of the damage zone in a notched tensile specimen is self-similar, i.e. the shape of the delamination front remains constant: it simply grows in scale. A simplified model of the damage is shown in Fig. 2. For an increment of split growth, δl , the energy absorbed in forming new crack surfaces, δE_{ab} , is given by [7-10]

$$\delta E_{ab} = G_s t \delta l + G_d (\ell \tan \alpha) \delta l, \quad (2)$$

where G_s is the energy absorbed per unit area of split; G_d is the energy absorbed per unit area of delamination; t is the thickness of a 0° ply; and α is the delamination angle at the split tip.

Some of the global energy of the system is dissipated when the split extends with a corresponding increase in specimen compliance, δC ,

$$\delta E_r = \frac{1}{2} P^2 \delta C. \quad (3)$$

For the damage zone to grow, $\delta E_r \geq \delta E_{ab}$,

$$\frac{1}{2} P^2 \delta C \geq G_s t \delta l + G_d \ell \delta l \tan \alpha \quad (4)$$

where P is the applied load on one quadrant only of the specimen (Fig. 2) given by

$$P = \sigma_\infty (W/2)(2t). \quad (5)$$

σ_∞ is the remote applied tensile stress on the specimen, and W is the specimen width.

For the limiting case, $E_r = E_{ab}$,

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{P^2}{t} \frac{\delta C}{\delta \ell} = G_s + G_d \frac{\ell \tan \alpha}{t} \quad (6)$$

(essentially, $G = G_c$).

G_c is the effective toughness of the laminate and G is the strain energy release rate. We have used a 2-D finite element model to determine $\delta C / \delta \ell$ numerically [7-10]. For a range of split length between $\ell / a = 0$ and $\ell / a = 6$, it turns out (fortunately) that $\delta C / \delta \ell$ is constant, its value dependent on the angle α , the lay-up construction of the laminate and temperature.

Re-arranging Eqn. (6), the load for split initiation is given by

$$P_i = \left[\frac{2G_s t}{\delta C / \delta \ell_{\ell=0}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

Quite simply, the value of G_s can be determined from a measurement of P_i . For subsequent split growth under monotonic loading,

$$\ell = \frac{P^2 (\delta C / \delta \ell)}{2G_d \tan \alpha} - \frac{G_s}{G_d} \left[\frac{t}{\tan \alpha} \right] \quad (8)$$

Dividing both sides of Eqn. (8) by notch length, a , and substituting for P (in terms of applied stress σ_∞), and $\delta C / \delta \ell$, [scaled from the finite element result $(\partial C / \partial \ell)_{FE}$], this expression can be normalised as follows,

$$\frac{\ell}{a} = \frac{(\sigma_\infty)^2 (t)(W/2)_{FE} (2t)_{FE}}{G_d \tan \alpha (2a/W)} \frac{\partial C}{\partial \ell} \Big|_{FE} - \frac{G_s}{G_d} \left[\frac{t}{a \tan \alpha} \right] \quad (9)$$

where $\partial C / \partial \ell$ is the change in compliance of the FE model with split length; $(W)_{FE}$ is the width of FE model specimen; and $(t)_{FE}$ is the ply thickness in the FE model.

Provided $G_s < G_d$ (it turns out that it is), then the second term on the right-hand side of Eqn. (9) is small, and can be ignored:

$$\frac{\ell}{a} = \frac{(\sigma_\infty)^2 (t)(W/2)_{FE} (2t)_{FE}}{G_d \tan \alpha (2a/W)} \frac{\partial C}{\partial \ell} \Big|_{FE} \quad (10)$$

INCORPORATION OF RESIDUAL STRESSES INTO THE FE MODEL

If thermal residual stresses are included in the model, then a simple compliance expression is no longer sufficient.

As the level of damage increases, three energy release contributions exist: (i) an increase in mesh-compliance caused by a change in the mechanical strain energy, (ii) a relaxation of the residual stresses and hence a decrease in the thermal strain energy of the mesh and (iii) a small expansion of the mesh due to relieving of the residual stresses and therefore a work contribution from the applied load. The expression for the total potential energy released now becomes

$$\partial E_r = \frac{1}{2} P^2 \partial C - \partial E_{th} + P \partial v \quad (11)$$

E_{th} is the strain energy due to residual stresses only and v is the displacement of the top edge of the FE mesh before loading, measured from the position at $\ell/a = 0$. At a fixed temperature, the elastic properties are constant and E_{th} is proportional to the square of the remote residual stress. Similarly, displacement is caused by damage alleviating thermal contraction; therefore v is directly proportional to the temperature drop applied and to the magnitude of the residual stress. Incorporating the mechanisms of splitting and delamination:

$$\frac{1}{2} P^2 \frac{\partial C}{\partial \ell} - \frac{\partial E_{th}}{\partial \ell} + P \frac{\partial v}{\partial \ell} = G_{st} + G_d (\tan \alpha) \ell \quad (12)$$

The compliance change $\partial C / \partial \ell$ of the FE mesh was calculated and shown to be independent of split length (Table 1). The functions of thermal strain energy $\partial E_{th} / \partial \ell$ and displacement $\partial v / \partial \ell$, however, were not independent of split length and were described using linear functions of ℓ/a (Tables 2 and 3). The rate of change of displacement was independent of specimen size for a constant $2a/W$, but thermal strain energy was scaled from the FE result. In a similar way as before:

$$\ell = \frac{\frac{1}{2} P^2 (\partial C / \partial \ell) - G_{st} - C_1 W t / W_{FE} t_{FE} + P C_3}{(G_d \tan \alpha + C_2 W t / a W_{FE} t_{FE} - P C_4 / a)} \quad (13)$$

If residual stresses are excluded from the analysis, C_1 - C_4 are equal to zero and Eqn. (13) simplifies to:

$$\ell = \frac{\frac{1}{2} P^2 (\partial C / \partial \ell) - G_{st}}{G_d \tan \alpha} \quad (14)$$

as derived originally by Kortschot, Beaumont and Ashby [9].

Substituting for P and $\partial C / \partial \ell$: and dividing both sides by the notch half-length, a , produces:

$$\frac{\ell}{a} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \sigma_{\infty}^2 W t (\partial C / \partial \ell)_{FE} W_{FE} t_{FE} - G_{st} - C_1 W t / W_{FE} t_{FE} + \sigma_{\infty} W t C_3}{(G_d \tan \alpha + C_2 W t / W_{FE} t_{FE} - \sigma_{\infty} W t C_4)} \quad (15)$$

CALCULATION OF G_s AND G_d

Values of G_s were determined from the stress to initiate damage, σ_{oi} , measured from x-ray radiography. At the onset of damage, the split length equals zero and Eqn. (15) can be rearranged to give:

$$G_s = \frac{\sigma_{oi}^2 W (\partial C / \partial \ell)_{FE} W_{FE} t_{FE}}{2} - \frac{C_1 W}{W_{FE} t_{FE}} + \sigma_{oi} W C_3 \quad (16)$$

where substitution of appropriate values from finite element analysis gives the energy required for unit area of 0° ply splitting. The work of fracture for delamination, G_d , was calculated for a (90/0)_s laminate made from Hercules (IM8) carbon fibre in amorphous polyether sulphone (ITA) at each temperature by fitting Eqn. (15) to the experimental data for split growth. In contrast, a similar lay-up was made of a toughened thermoset of cyanate esters embedded with IM8 carbon fibres (Cyanate/IM8). For Cyanate/IM8, the delamination angle increased with stress and a linear function of the form $N\sigma$ was substituted for α , where N was a constant determined for each temperature. The results for ITA/IM8 and Cyanate/IM8 are shown in Figures 3 and 4 respectively, with the values of G_s and G_d tabulated in Table 4.

Table 1 Compliance Results

Temperature (°C)	ITA/IM8 $\partial C/\partial \ell$ (N ⁻¹)	Cyanate/IM8 $\partial C/\partial \ell$ (N ⁻¹)
20	4.15×10^{-14}	5.12×10^{-14}
120	4.34×10^{-14}	8.58×10^{-14}
180	4.44×10^{-14}	1.00×10^{-13}
200	4.97×10^{-14}	2.61×10^{-13}
225	2.33×10^{-13}	6.31×10^{-13}
250		1.29×10^{-12}

Table 2 Thermal Strain Energy Results

Temperature (°C)	ITA/IM8 $\partial U_{II}/\partial \ell$ (N)	Cyanate/IM8 $\partial U_{II}/\partial \ell$ (N)
20	$9.32 \times 10^1 - 1.59 \times 10^3(\ell/a)$	$-9.68 \times 10^1 - 1.57 \times 10^3(\ell/a)$
120	$4.01 \times 10^1 - 3.62 \times 10^2(\ell/a)$	$2.23 \times 10^1 - 8.86 \times 10^2(\ell/a)$
180	$9.42 \times 10^0 - 5.84 \times 10^1(\ell/a)$	$2.36 \times 10^0 - 5.76 \times 10^1(\ell/a)$
200	$-1.79 \times 10^0 - 1.34 \times 10^1(\ell/a)$	$-1.27 \times 10^1 - 2.61 \times 10^1(\ell/a)$
225	$-1.41 \times 10^{-3} - 1.13 \times 10^0(\ell/a)$	$-3.34 \times 10^{-1} - 4.00 \times 10^0(\ell/a)$
250		0

Table 3 Displacement Results

Temperature (°C)	ITA/IM8 $\partial v/\partial \ell$	Cyanate/IM8 $\partial v/\partial \ell$
20	$4.98 \times 10^{-7} + 4.44 \times 10^{-7}(\ell/a)$	$8.09 \times 10^{-7} + 6.16 \times 10^{-7}(\ell/a)$
120	$2.84 \times 10^{-7} + 1.09 \times 10^{-7}(\ell/a)$	$7.86 \times 10^{-7} + 6.69 \times 10^{-7}(\ell/a)$
180	$1.10 \times 10^{-7} + 8.71 \times 10^{-8}(\ell/a)$	$2.83 \times 10^{-7} + 2.14 \times 10^{-7}(\ell/a)$
200	$7.25 \times 10^{-8} + 5.40 \times 10^{-8}(\ell/a)$	$3.21 \times 10^{-7} + 2.49 \times 10^{-7}(\ell/a)$
225	$7.81 \times 10^{-8} + 6.35 \times 10^{-8}(\ell/a)$	$2.33 \times 10^{-7} + 1.81 \times 10^{-7}(\ell/a)$
250		0

The curves of split growth for ITA/IM8 are dominated by the relationship between ℓ/a and σ^2 . Theoretical curves for Cyanate/IM8 compare well with the experimental data, but have an alternative form to those in Figure 4. The delamination angle increases as a function of σ and the increasing area of 0/90 delamination surface controls the pattern of damage growth.

As the temperature is raised, the values of G_s and G_d generally increase for both materials. The greater ductility of the matrix increases its work of fracture and the energy required per unit area of new crack surface rises accordingly. Both materials at 20°C have a similar energy for splitting, but the values of G_d differ in accordance with the toughness of the matrix materials. At elevated temperatures, G_s for Cyanate/IM8 exceeds that for ITA/IM8, while the delamination energies G_d for both materials approach the same value.

Table 4

Temperature (°C)	ITA/IM8		Cyanate/IM8	
	G_S	G_D	G_S	G_D
20	76	736	73	493
120	79	714	89	541
180	80	688	102	720
200	89	443	265	834
225	236	1374	409	1365
250			702	879

Figure 3 Split Growth as a Function of Applied Stress for $[90/0]_s$ ITA/IM8. The smooth curves represent theoretical split growth rates

Figure 4 Split Growth as a Function of Stress for $[90/0]_s$ Cyanate/IM8. The smooth curves represent theoretical split growth rates

The total driving force for damage propagation comprises of three separate energy contributions (Eqn. (11)). In establishing the relative size of these contributions, difficulties arise due to the dependence of both $\partial E_{th} / \partial \ell$ and $\partial v / \partial \ell$ on ℓ / a , which in turn is a function of σ_{∞} . In order to examine the effect of excluding residual stresses from the analysis, values of G_s and G_d were calculated using only the contribution due to increasing compliance.

In the absence of any thermal stresses, both G_s and G_d decreased; the maximum difference being around 10% at 20°C. The residual stress contribution is proportional to the delamination angle; a thin delamination zone giving rise to stiff coupling between the 0° and 90° plies. For ITA/IM8 and Cyanate/IM8, residual stresses therefore have only a small part to play in driving the growth of subcritical damage – the majority of the available energy arises from a change in specimen compliance. Damage growth for both materials increases around the T_g , the point where specimen compliance is greatest.

COMPARISON WITH MEASURED FRACTURE TOUGHNESS VALUES

The values of G_s for splitting are expected to lie between the mode I and mode II interlaminar toughness values. The energies for delamination G_d , in contrast, are predicted to be of the order of the mode II shear toughness, G_{IIc} .

The results in Table 4 illustrate that this is not the case for G_s , where the values are considerably lower than would be expected from the measurements of toughness [16]. Likewise, the results for G_d while more appropriate, are still up to 50% below the shear toughness, G_{IIc} . Spearing *et al* recorded values of $G_s = 400 \text{ J/m}^2$ and $G_d = 800 \text{ J/m}^2$ for carbon fibre/PEEK, compared with mode I and II toughness values in the range 1.5-2.5 kJ/m^2 . They conjectured that the absence of residual stresses in the energy balance calculation resulted in altered values of the fracture energies being obtained. The results show that the inclusion of residual stresses produces a rise of up to 10% in G_s and G_d for ITA/IM8 and Cyanate/IM8. In all cases, however, the fracture energies predicted from the model remain considerably below the values measured from fracture mechanics tests. These discrepancies in G_s and G_d can be partially attributed to the method of calculation of the driving force for damage propagation.

A DAMAGE MODEL FOR QUASI-STATIC AND POST-FATIGUE STRENGTH

Using a finite element representation of the damage at a notch tip, combined with the observed terminal damage-state and measured failure stress, Kortschot and Beaumont [7-10] showed that the maximum tensile stress in the principal load bearing (0°) ply was approximately constant at laminate failure, regardless of the extent of damage. This led them to propose a straightforward tensile stress failure criterion;

$$\sigma_{\infty f} = \frac{\sigma_{0f}}{K_t}, \quad (17)$$

where $\sigma_{\infty f}$ is the remote failure stress of the notched laminate; σ_{0f} is the localised tensile strength of the (0°) ply in the damage zone; and K_t is the terminal notch tip stress concentration factor. σ_{0f} is a material property which can be determined independently while K_t can be obtained from finite element modelling. For a centre-notched (90/0)_s specimen K_t is found to be [7-10];

$$K_t = \frac{6.3}{[1 - (2a/W)^2]^{0.28} (\ell/a)^{0.28}} = C_5 \left[\frac{\ell}{a} \right]^{-0.28}. \quad (18)$$

Furthermore, the local strength of a 0° ply within the notch tip damage zone of a centre-notched tensile (CNT) specimen depends on the size of the damaged zone (just like the strength of brittle solids depend on their volume);

$$\sigma_{0f} = \sigma_0 \left[\frac{V_0}{KV_{CNT}} \right]^{1/m}, \quad (19)$$

where σ_0 , V_0 is a mean failure stress and reference volume (typically 1.88 GPa and 7.4 mm³, respectively, in Kortschot's experiments), for the 0° ply in a waisted (unnotched) (90/0)_s tensile specimen. K_{CNT} is the equivalent volume of the 0° ply in the notch tip damage zone; and m is the Weibull modulus.

The stress distribution at the notch tip varies with split length, ℓ , and the delamination angle, α , at the tip of the split. In Kortschot's experiments, $\alpha = 3.5^\circ$, $K = 0.0014 + 0.0025 (\ell/a)$; hence

$$\sigma_{0f} = \sigma_0 \left\{ \frac{V_0}{[0.0014 + 0.0025(\ell/a)8(a^2t)]} \right\}^{1/m} \quad (20)$$

$$= C_6 \{ [0.0014 + 0.0025(\ell/a)] a^2 \}^{-1/m} \quad (21)$$

$V_{CNT} = 8(a^2t)$, where t is the thickness of the 0° ply.

Figure 5 shows K_t results for ITA/IM8 using a constant delamination angle of 0.7°. Thermal strain mismatch between the 0° and 90° plies causes a state of residual compression parallel to the fibres in the load-bearing 0° ply. This reduces the maximum tensile stress and hence reduces K_t . As temperature is increased, K_t increases due to two mechanisms: (i) a reduction in the level of residual stress and (ii) a decrease in the lamina transverse and shear moduli. The latter causes an increase in the anisotropy of the specimen, forcing the 0° ply to carry a greater proportion of the applied load. If $\log(K_t)$ is plotted against $\log(\ell/a)$, straight lines can be fitted to the data for each temperature using the empirical function of the form:

$$K_t = \frac{C_5}{(\ell/a)^p} \quad (22)$$

where C_5 and p are constants (Figure 6).

Figure 5 Stress Concentration Factor as a Function of ℓ/a for ITA/IM8

Figure 6 Stress Concentration Factor as a Function of l/a for ITA/IM8

K_t results for Cyanate/IM8 are presented in Figure 7 and a decreasing K_t is found as the temperature is raised. The finite element meshes for Cyanate/IM8 were constructed, however, with increasing values of α with temperature (in contrast to ITA/IM8 where α was constant). The increasing width of the delamination zone with temperature overrides the effect due to residual stresses and increasing anisotropy. A large delamination zone reduces shear coupling across the split and results in a lower value of K_t . It should be noted that the meshes for both 120°C and 180°C were constructed with a value α of 1.3°. The delamination zones are therefore of equal size and the values of K_t for 180°C in Figure 7 are greater than those for 120°C due to temperature influences only.

Figure 7 Stress Concentration Factor as a Function of l/a for Cyanate/IM8

WEIBULL TESTS AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

The strength of a 0° ply in the highly stressed region at the notch tip of a CNT specimen can be determined by measuring the mean strength of specimens having a known value of KV. Experiments were undertaken on unnotched centrally-waisted [90/0]_s specimens of ITA/IM8 and Cyanate/IM8 at five test temperatures up to 250°C.

After testing, the strength data for each temperature were assigned median ranks and were plotted on Weibull paper as $\ln(\ln(1/P_s))$ against $\ln(\sigma)$. Figure 8 shows the results of Weibull testing at 20°C and 200°C for ITA/IM8; the Weibull modulus being calculated from the gradient of the best-fit straight line. A summary of the results for both materials is given in Table 6.

Figure 8 Weibull Plot of Strength Data for ITA/IM8 at 20°C and 200°C

Table 5 Results from Weibull Experiments

Temperature (°C)	ITA/IM8		Cyanate/IM8	
	$\bar{\sigma}$ (MPa)	m	$\bar{\sigma}$ (MPa)	m
20	3008	13.0	2793	12.6
120	2842	12.9	2555	16.3
180	2725	9.8	2134	11.8
200	2413	10.2	1852	9.32
225	2196	11.3		
250			1820	8.82

KV calculation for the waisted specimens was performed using a stress-volume integral derived by Hitchon *et al* [17].

Weibull moduli exhibit no consistent trend with increasing temperature, but all results lie between 8 and 16. This range corresponds with a value of 11 measured for a carbon fibre/PEEK system by Spearing *et al* [15].

APPLICATION TO THE CNT SPECIMEN NOTCH TIP

The stress field at the tip of a notch in a CNT specimen was determined by finite element analysis. To determine KV_{CNT} , the finite element results were scaled from a 2-layer quadrant to the dimensions of the actual specimen by defining a reference volume $V_{CNT} = 8a^2t_0$ (a is the notch half-length and t_0 is half the total thickness of the 0° plies). K was obtained by integrating numerically using finite element results (Kortschot *et al*).

Figure 10 shows the results of K plotted against normalised split length for Cyanate/IM8. As split length increases, the stress gradients at the notch tip become less severe and a larger volume of material is subjected to a stress close to the peak stress. An increase in temperature results in a larger value of K due to the increasing size of the delamination zone. A larger angle α corresponds to more compliant shear coupling across the split and hence a larger equivalent volume. The results for ITA/IM8, in contrast, show little variation of K with temperature as the finite element meshes were constructed with a constant delamination angle of 0.7° .

In order to describe K as a function of ℓ/a , empirical equations of the form:

$$K = C_6 \left(\frac{\ell}{a} \right) \tag{23}$$

were fitted through the data, where C_6 is a constant (Table 6).

Figure 9 Stress/Volume Integral (K) as a Function of ℓ/a for Cyanate/IM8

Table 6 K Results

Temperature (°C)	ITA/IM8 C_2	Cyanate/IM8 C_2
20	0.00357	0.00237
120	0.00364	0.00496
180	0.00509	0.00712
200	0.00462	0.00927
225	0.00353	0.0132
250		0.0162

If Eqn. (23) is inserted into Eqn. (19), the full expression for the strength of the U ply at each temperature becomes:

$$\sigma_{0f} = \sigma_0 \left[\frac{V_0}{C_6(\ell/a)8a^2t_0} \right]^{1/m} \quad (24)$$

where σ_0 , V_0 and m are measured from Weibull experiments and C_6 is calculated using finite element results.

Experimental values of Weibull modulus were observed to be constant up to the T_g , indicating little change in the population of dominant flaws.

APPLICATION OF THE TENSILE FAILURE CRITERION

The remote stress on the notched specimen at failure is given by:

$$\sigma_{\infty f} = \sigma_0 \left[\frac{V_0}{C_6(\ell/a)8a^2t_0} \right]^{1/m} \left[\frac{(\ell/a)^p}{C_5} \right] \quad (25)$$

The remote failure stress is a function of the damage state, characterised by ℓ/a , at the point of failure. For typical values of p and m calculated previously, longer split lengths correspond to higher strength specimens. Equation (25) therefore requires an experimental measurement of the split length immediately prior to catastrophic failure to determine $\sigma_{\infty f}$. Stable damage growth was modelled as a function of applied stress (Equation (15)). For a $[90/0]_s$ lay-up, substituting for ℓ/a in Eqn (25) produces:

$$\sigma_{\infty f} = C_7 a^{-2/m} \left[\frac{\frac{1}{2} \sigma_{\infty f}^2 Wt(\partial C/\partial \ell)_{FE} W_{FE} t_{FE} - G_s t - C_1 Wt / W_{FE} t_{FE} + \sigma_{\infty f} Wt C_3}{(G_d a \tan \alpha + C_2 Wt / W_{FE} t_{FE} - \sigma_{\infty f} Wt C_4)} \right]^{(p-1/m)} \quad (26)$$

where C_7 is a dimensional constant which must be determined for each temperature and material type. Eqn. (26) incorporates an implicit calculation of the damage state at failure and results in a remote strength prediction which is based entirely on independently determined parameters. The fracture energies, G_s and G_d , were calculated by curve fitting using the experimental data for damage growth, but no reference has been made to the data for tensile strength. An equation of this type, without inclusion of residual stresses, was originally derived by Kortschot, Beaumont and Ashby [9] to describe the effect of notch size on composite tensile strength.

COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Eqn. (26) was solved at various temperatures using an iterative computational method. Figure 11 presents the experimental strength results for ITA/IM8, plotted alongside the values predicted by the damage-based model. The predicted results for $[90_2/0_2]_s$ were calculated entirely from data generated for a reference $[90/0]_s$ lay-up. Agreement is generally very good, with predicted values falling within the range of experimental scatter. An overestimation of the strength at 180°C can be attributed to a slightly low value of modulus, m , measured from Weibull analysis (see Table 6).

The results for Cyanate/IM8 are given in Figure 11 and the strength model again corresponds well with experimental values. Above 150°C , however, predicted strengths for $[90_2/0_2]_s$ are around 15% greater than those measured by tensile testing. Difficulties arose in modelling damage growth for a variable α and the split growth rates predicted for $[90_2/0_2]_s$ were considerably greater than those observed from x-ray radiography. This results in an overestimation of the notch blunting effect and hence a correspondingly higher ultimate strength.

Figure 10 Notched Tensile Strength of ITA/IM8 - Experimental Results and Predictions from the Damage-Based Model

Figure 11 Notched Tensile Strength of Cyanate/IM8 - Experimental Results and Predictions from the Damage-Based Model

Notched strength behaviour for both materials is dominated by a decrease in the 0° ply unnotched strength with temperature (Table 6). At 250°C, however, the notched failure strength of Cyanate/IM8 exceeds that measured at 200°C. The split length at failure at 250°C is around $l/a = 14$, while at 200°C, a value of only $l/a = 5$ is obtained. The rate of split growth increases with temperature and the notch blunting effect has become sufficient at 250°C to cause an 8% rise in the ultimate notched strength. Kortschot [private communication] observed a similar increasing strength effect at high temperature and associated it with enhanced splitting and matrix debonding.

CONCLUSIONS

Thermal residual stresses were included into the model, but were found to influence the fracture energies, G_s and G_d , by less than 10%. Additional energy contributions were suggested that may arise due to interlaminar effects not included in the 2-dimensional finite element model.

The predictions of failure strength produced excellent agreement with experimental results and confirmed the applicability of a damage-based model across a range of elevated temperatures albeit for two different material types only.

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